

THE STATE OF BUDGET AND FINANCIAL SITUATION AND ACTIVITY IN THE COUNTRY TODAY

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ABSTRACT

Part of state activity within the state budget process. Some of the measures implemented by the ministries and agencies lead to additional costs from the document production. Participation with the participation of the state is being implemented. Long years between the levels of budgets incomes and due to clearly strengthening the authority to transfer aid the amount and effectiveness of funds in government bodies. There was no security support. In addition, to the ongoing activity by the individual state the participation of the state in the economic economy continues. That's it in connection with the state's participation in the economy it is necessary to carry out corrections in the activity of state power. Based on the above, the proposed profit budget ensuring stability and connections between the levels of the State budget about. State budget completeness, reliability and strategic State budget all state special purpose funds and in off-budget personal treasury accounts of budgetary organizations view money for adding funds to the State budget, budget in the report of the State Budget and State Target Funds presentation of consolidated total indicators in a single form necessary.

When assessing the current state of an organization's financial controls, begin by determining which financial processes pose the greatest risk. One-way internal auditors can assess financial controls is by looking at all of the functions and processes in accounting and finance and asking if a process were "broken" and activities were not getting done correctly, how much trouble would that cause organization? For example, if for some reason checks were not cut or the accounts payable system did not function and vendors were not paid, goods and services would no longer be coming in and things would get dicey. In this example, the cash disbursements process would be an area where internal auditors would want strong financial controls in place. Additionally, within the cash disbursements processes, employees could set up fictitious vendors, cut fraudulent checks, or make deals with vendors to defraud the operation. Another example of an area where strong controls are absolutely essential

would be within the payroll function. Payroll is such a huge expense for everyone¹. Operations that the slightest weakness or gap in the controls could have disastrous results. Employees could be paid incorrectly — or not at all — and once again, unscrupulous employees could exploit gaps and weaknesses in the controls to perpetrate frauds such as having fictitious employees on the payroll, not recording vacation or other paid time off, or overpaying themselves, relatives, and friends. Unfortunately, there will always be people who try to perpetrate fraud, and internal auditors need to stay one step ahead.

In addition to the potential for fraud in the operation, without strong financial controls it would be easy for innocent mistakes (e.g., misposting to the general ledger or forgetting to book an entry) to allow a major reporting error to go undetected and cause management to make an incorrect decision, which could potentially cost large amounts of money. Strong financial controls not only help prevent and detect fraud, but they also help detect true mistakes in accounting and management reporting.

American Depositary Shares are denominated in USD. Initiated, the profit company deponenlled in the country to the maximum amount of securities. The U.S. is valuable in asserting a relative ownership stake paper is counted. American depositories certain movement America is a certificate confirming ownership of depository shares. The depository identifies the securities as international securities and the mechanism of being on the map requires certain steps. Depository receipts are issued on the basis of special legislation existence and such legislation exists in the United States such securities are called American Depositary Receipts (ADRs). Direct ownership of shares (or bonds) of companies for depository receipts not giving the right to do. from depository receipts representing debt relationship is widespread in the world, especially in Latin America in their countries they are widely used². The advantages of issuing ADRI for issuers are, first of all, their activities if it attracts additional capital, it is to raise the position of the company. ADRIarni benefits for investors include:

- Injuring the purchase of high-yield shares to the shares of national companies;
- buy shares of direct purchase companies relatively low risk compared to receiving;
- sufficient knowledge of capital stock markets and to the stock market of another country under the same conditions output creation;
- income received in national currency with currency risk lack of need for conversion.

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¹ BUDGET AND FINANCIAL PLANNING GLOBAL INNOVATIVE LEADERSHIP MODULE

² J.K. ATANIYAZOV, E.D. ALIMARDONOV INTERNATIONAL FINANCE RELATIONSHIPS

treasury accounts of budgetary organizations view money for adding funds to the State budget, budget in the report of the State Budget and State Target Funds presentation of consolidated total indicators in a single form necessary. More effective and continuous provision of public finance management products depending on the budgets of the united budget holder, taking into account net income and sources of receipt inter-budgetary relations between the republic and the respective budgets ta necessary necessary. Second, the openness, completeness and internationality of budget data the purpose of ensuring compliance with standards, transparent and reliable regarding state resources and extensive background checks Public Finance Management serves to carry out the rise of the being carried out³. Comprehensiveness, comparability of public finance data and strategic indicators to monitor the integrity of the tax-budget policy in the introduction of profit, of funds allocated from profit complete, timely and reliable in transition to productivity providing a source of information.

Investment funds - this is a profit between the population by taking their shares collecting funds through distribution, and then a special state to loans, state treasury opportunities investment services and valuable is an open joint-stock company that performs transactions of buying and selling securities. Consists of the income of investment funds: consists of them dividends on purchased shares and securities income from transactions⁴. Investment activity in the TOP of special activities of the fund. Shares and valuables of investment funds production of all transactions with papers in the depository. Authorized management of investment fund assets, fund management. Direct relationship manager by way of payment will be handed over to the company. The peculiarity of the activity of investment funds is transactions accounting also has a special effect. International privatized investment responding to accounting standards. Plan of funds accounts has been adopted. Generally accepted chart of accounts based on which only new accounts are added. These are the accounts privatized mutual fund assets capital, income and analytical determination of income statement.

Finance is directly related to the sale of public economic relations on the accumulation and redistribution of centralized and decentralized funds of the fund. In the evolutionary process, humanity moved from commodity exchange to commodity-money relations, this money became a universal equivalent, and the state began to manage its activities, incomes and their management of economic and social processes. water in the form of money forming various monetary funds.

Money is the measurable equivalent of labor. Finance serves nationally through the economic way of gross social product and income distribution. They are means of controlling the production and distribution of material goods; treatment of the state and society. Finance abstracted all the processes taking place in the state, economic economy and social processes, but also politics, ecology, demography, etc. The production of any work in the state cannot be carried out without redistribution of resources, i.e., without activity in the field of the state of legal implementation.

³ Assistance in the state financial system in Uzbekistan and prospects Inomjon Toraevich Jumaniozov
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⁴ D. Q. USMONOVA ACCOUNTING ACCOUNT STUDY MANUAL 2020

THE PERCENTAGE OF AMERICANS WHO ARE STRUGGLING OR IN CRISIS WITH THEIR FINANCES IS TRENDING DOWN.

THE STATE OF PERSONAL FINANCE IN AMERICA

RAMSEY

When asked about the overall state of their personal finances, about a third of Americans (30%) said they're either struggling or in crisis. That's a decline of nearly 19% from the high in Q3 of 2022 (37%). Breaking this data down further, more women than men feel insecure about their financial status (38% vs. 21%), and millennials are the most likely to struggle (37%). Baby boomers, who generally earn more income and have more assets than the younger generations, are the most stable with only 22% saying they're struggling or in crisis⁵.

Finance is always an economic situation, a phenomenon that exists only in commodity-money relations. The importance of finance in the state depends on the position of commodity-money relations in the state. From this, the role of finance comes or increases. Until the 1990s, power law did not exist in the strict sense, it was replaced by administrative law. But not all money relationships mean relationships. Money transactions, sales of goods, accounting and control of money are not represented by sales relations. Finance is different from money. If money is the universal equivalent of social labor, then finance is an economic category that describes the process of distribution of funds in such a state in a centralized or decentralized manner. Finance is the economic costs of distribution and redistribution of social product and total national income. This is a kind of control over the profit of funds. The purpose of finance is to ensure that educational income and funds are allocated to the state, but also to the funds of organizations and citizens, and also to ensure ruble control over the use of funds. Finance represents money relations, the income of which is the systematic transfer, distribution and subsequent transportation of money and funds of the state, people and population.

Today's economic series of news and changes is the current economic economic is serving further improvement for help. state, institutional in the direction of state finance is being implemented on a large scale. At the basis of these practices, first of all, the state the implementation of the budget is recognized by the world and tested in the countries of the

⁵ The State of Personal Finance in America Q1 2023

world, effective from the budget funds. Acknowledgment of the settlement through the treasury practice is must. The honor of independence to effectively organize the treasury execution of the state budget in our country, success was achieved only after we obtained indicators for personal, specific things. The Republic of Uzbekistan also has a wide coverage of the public finance management system trying to give a rising result. State high level of such reforms. It can be said that the successful implementation of the budget is evident. Treasury execution of the state budget includes all revenues of the state budget and state special funds, for, the single treasury of budget receipts from extra-budgetary funds Aggregate to the account number and account for the implementation of all resources of the page from the partner. This is the state budget, additional funds from the budget, to carry out rapid control and monitoring of state debts and the process of servicing them, on provision of resources of state funds, movement of resources of state resources on gathering operational external information. Today, when our modern society is developing, the economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan integration of deep economic problems in the state financial system of liberalization and modernization is increasing. This development, along with the management of public finances takes into account the sign. In doing so, it is necessary to ensure the management and methods of state finances, scientific collection, processing, production of information using the progress of technical development and other technical means to demand further increase of informatization based on mastering procedures and methods. Support in the management of state finances. Public finances are the main link of the state budget management, production of budget process organization system, cashier in budget execution from the system when world practices are protected from the test and the budget showing its loaded dead. Implementation of the transition to the implementation of the system of budget funds in the treasury of our country is economic will be one of the achievements. Based on the current modern economy, it can be said that the budget process is organized effectively the practical work of doing it cannot be imagined outside the control of the treasury. It is even modern. In addition to scientists and economists, advanced specialists in the field of economics are also a reasonable approach confessor. After all, the treasury system is the only treasury of revenues and earnings The right and effective way to attract cash flows to the account number, actions, actions and implementation of the first and current control, in this way, execution of the state budget at a higher level serves to expand the inspection. It is useful in the management of public finances in the country, as well as in the implementation of the state budget One of the mechanisms is considered to be foreign in the production and management of the treasury It occupies the place of the country's most important ones. Uzbekistan will not be a simple copy through them, because administration organization of state administration, regulation of economic and legal relations is a country with its own direction. to do, thereby organizing and developing the treasury the learning level of experiences in the direction is not passive⁶.

⁶ International conference on developments in the field of education Hosted from Amsterdam, Netherlands
<https://econferencezone.org> June 8 2022 THE STATE OF THE CURRENT TREASURY SYSTEM ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM Shodmonkulova Shakhlo.

EU net financial worth, Q1 2008 - Q3 2022

(% of GDP and € billion)

eurostat

The net financial worth can change either due to transactions or due to other economic flows (mainly price changes, also known as holding gains or losses). The main financial instrument liabilities on the general government's balance sheet are debt securities. As these are traded on the financial markets, the value of these instruments changes over time and can be volatile.

In recent quarters, the existing stock of debt securities has decreased in market value at the EU level, notably due to increases in interest rates. A major part of financial assets on the balance sheet of EU governments are equity and investment fund shares or units, mainly comprising shares held in public corporations. These include the shares held in the National Central Bank, the value of which is influenced by the revaluation of the monetary reserves. At EU level, the increase in the value of equity and investment fund shares or units and the decreased value of debt securities contributed to an improvement in net financial worth in recent quarters. At the same time, the continued EU general government deficit (measured as transactions in financial assets minus the transactions in liabilities) contributed negatively to the net financial worth⁷.

Business entities in the process of deepening the economy future production by analyzing economic development at the macro and micro levels predicting the volume of output (work and service), efficiency making decisions that are important for "Accounting". Enquires further improvement of the methodology. About the analysis important decisions are taken directly by the firm to improve management correction. If so, this data is the economy of the goods to the operation of the activity and the arrival of additional investment land state.

In conclusion, the goal set before our research and it is achieved in effective ways authors for special literature and normative documents, series in the process of studying,

⁷ Government finance statistics: net financial worth Product Code DDN-20230123-1

analyzing and researching everyday experiences be able to issue scientifically based administrations. These are the main ones given. Part of state activity within the state budget process. Some of the measures implemented by the ministries and agencies lead to additional costs from the document production. Participation with the participation of the state is being implemented.

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